

1 **Highlights**

- 2 • Evolution of mineralogy, possible reactions, and type of atmosphere are presented
- 3 • Mineralogical comparison is conducted considering the aggregate loss on ignition
- 4 • New mineral phases, such as mullite or hercynite, are produced in the aggregates
- 5 • The presence and percentage of new minerals are influenced by the added iron phase
- 6 • Cork powder and sodium carbonate play an important role in the atmosphere type

Mineralogical evolution of artificial aggregates manufactured with different iron phases

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54 **Abstract**

55
56 A selection of fifty-one artificial aggregates, manufactured with different proportions of
57 kaolinite, an iron phase (Fe^0 , Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4 or FeS_2), cork powder and sodium carbonate
58 in three previous works, have been studied mineralogically using the quantitative Rietveld
59 XRD method. Comparisons between the mineral percentage in the raw materials and the
60 phase percentage in the aggregate have been carried out. Additionally, independence
61 contrast tests have been conducted to determine if significant relationships exist between
62 the raw material mineralogical composition and the aggregate phase composition. Based
63 on these statistical results, the mineralogical evolution, the possible reactions that may
64 have taken place and the type of atmosphere required for them have been presented.
65 Mullite, metallic iron, cristobalite, hematite, magnetite, hercynite, fayalite,
66 clinopyroxenes, troilite, nepheline and amorphous material were new phases produced in
67 the aggregates. The presence and/or percentage of the majority of them were greatly
68 influenced by the added iron phase and by the type of atmosphere in the aggregates. In
69 the latter, cork powder and/or sodium carbonate addition played an important role since
70 their thermal decomposition could give rise to different conditions (oxidizing, reducing
71 or both) depending on whether it is the external or internal zone of the aggregates
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73 **Keywords:** Artificial aggregate; Iron phases; Loss on ignition; Mineralogical
74 composition; Phase composition; Rietveld XRD
75

76 **Abbreviations:** *AA*: artificial aggregate; *Am. Ph.*: amorphous phase; *BI*: bloating index;
77 *Ck*: cork powder; *Ckt*: cookeite; *Clp*: clinopyroxene; *Crs*: cristobalite; *Eq.*: equation; *Ex*:
78 external; *Fa*: fayalite; *Fe*: metallic iron; *GoF*: goodness of fit; *Hc*: hercynite; *Hem*:
79 hematite; *Ill*: illite; *In*: internal; *IP*: iron phase; *Krc*: kaolinite-rich component; *Kln*:
80 kaolinite; *LOI*: loss on ignition; *LOI (1+2)*: LOI during the preheating and heating phases
81 in the rotary kiln; *LWA*: lightweight aggregate; *Mag*: magnetite; *Mul*: mullite; *Nat*:
82 natrite; *Nep*: nepheline; *N.I.P*: no iron phase; *Py*: pyrite; *Qtz*: quartz; *Rc.*: chemical
83 reaction; *Rhb*: rombloclase; *RM*: raw material; *rs*: Spearman's correlation coefficient;
84 *Rwp*: weighted R profile; R^2 : coefficient of determination; *S*: compressive strength;
85 *SRM*: standard reference material; T^a : heating temperature; *Tro*: troilite; *WA₂₄*: water
86 absorption after 24 hours; *XRD*: X-ray diffraction; ρ_b : bulk density; *prd*: dry particle
87 density
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1. INTRODUCTION

Aggregates can be defined as granular materials used in construction which can be natural, artificial or recycled. *Artificial aggregate (AA)* is that of mineral origin resulting from an industrial process that involves thermal or other modification. If they also present a loose bulk density (ρ_b) not exceeding 1.20 g/cm³ or with a particle density not exceeding 2.00 g/cm³ are defined as artificial *lightweight aggregates (LWAs)* [1]. The manufacture of *AAs* has become an activity of great interest since they can be produced from a wide variety of residues (both organic and inorganic), also allowing the utilization of contaminated wastes, since the immobilization of certain metals in the *AA* has been demonstrated [2]. If, additionally, the artificial aggregate obtained is “lightweight”, the benefits increase, due to the properties that this type of aggregate presents, particularly lightness and low thermal conductivity.

First, it is known that the composition and/or mineralogical composition of the raw materials used for the manufacture of artificial lightweight aggregates will influence the phase composition of the synthesised aggregates. At the same time, previous studies show that the phase composition of aggregate influences their technological properties, and in the technological properties of the composites that are going to be manufactured with them, such as lightweight concrete. In previous studies, little consideration is given to quantitative comparison between the mineralogical phases and/or amorphous material of the raw materials and the new phases produced in the aggregates, especially taking into account the loss on ignition that the raw materials have suffered during the preheating and heating phases in the rotary kiln (*LOI (1+2)*).

Secondly, it is also known that the presence of iron compounds in the raw materials give rise to expanded aggregates as many release gases during the heating process [3,4]. Studies of such raw materials containing iron compounds are numerous (e.g. [5,6]). In 1951, one of the first researchers to explore this was Riley [4]: in order to determine the minerals responsible for expansion, Riley prepared mixtures to obtain artificial expanded aggregates, concluding that pyrite and hematite, among others, can produce gas at a sufficiently high temperature to cause expansion. Also, Cubaud and Murat, in 1968 [7], presented a compilation of different decomposition reactions of iron-bearing mineral constituents leading to gas evolution and the resulting phase composition. Over the years, and especially from the beginning of the 21st century, the number of scientific studies related to the production of artificial aggregates using iron-bearing raw materials has increased considerably. Yang *et al.* [8] studied the production of lightweight aggregates by the mixtures of low-silicon iron tailing, quartz sand and fly ash. All of them presented bloating potential at high temperature, where hematite, quartz and anorthite are the main phases of the LWAs. Wei and Ko [9] found that the iron oxide components in the steel sludges used act as flux for the artificial aggregate production as well as the disappearance of quartz after sintering is related with the glassy surface formation in the aggregates. Those published by Moreno-Maroto *et al.* [10,11,12] are also noteworthy as they present the relationship between the percentages of multicomponent mixtures containing Fe, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄ or FeS₂ with the technological properties of the synthesised aggregates, using statistical methods and delving into the effect that the iron species would have in the reaction schemes. The study presented here is part of a broader research programme that builds on of the findings of Moreno-Maroto *et al.* [10,11,12] and whose specific objectives are presented below.

Lastly, a detailed and in-depth knowledge of the mineral formation processes in artificial aggregates, from those found in their raw materials (possible reactions, relationship with the raw material percentage...) in addition to the conditions of their synthesis (temperature and firing time, redox conditions...). This will allow the composition and

154 processing conditions to be optimised. In particular, the knowledge of how the addition
155 of one iron phase or another component as raw materials can influence the phase
156 composition of the resulting aggregate could be considered as an important aspect in the
157 aggregate manufacturing process with iron-rich materials or wastes.

158 This paper intends to present an innovative procedure to carry out a robust comparison of
159 the mineralogical composition of the raw materials and the aggregates obtained from
160 them; allowing a manufacturer to establish the amount of a crystalline phase that reacts
161 during firing, or is transformed to give rise to another, newly formed product phase.

162 The specific objectives of this research work are:

163 *i)* to determine quantitatively the mineralogical changes that occurred in artificial
164 aggregates produced with different pure iron phases as well as the proportion of
165 amorphous reaction products;

166 *ii)* to establish how the initial composition of the raw materials (compounds and their
167 proportions) as well as the sintering conditions, have influenced the phase composition
168 found in the aggregates studied;

169 *iii)* to demonstrate the importance of using quantitative methods of determination,
170 together with statistical analysis versus semi-quantitative methods. Moreover, this
171 work aims to establish the foundation for future studies that would determine the
172 influence of the phase composition of the aggregates, on their technological properties
173 of synthetic aggregates.

174 175 2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

176 177 2.1. INITIAL COMPOSITIONS OF THE STUDIED ARTIFICIAL 178 AGGREGATES

179 A selection of fifty-one artificial aggregates (Tables S1-S5, Supplementary Material)
180 produced in the three previous studies [10,11,12] have been studied in terms of their
181 composition. They were manufactured with different proportions of four components:

182 *i)* kaolinite-rich component (*Krc*), as basic aluminosilicate-rich clay mineral. Its
183 proportion varied between 40 % and 100% by mass;

184 *ii)* an iron phase (*IP*), as iron donor and source of gases. This *component* was one of the
185 following: *ii.a)* metallic iron (*Fe*); *ii.b)* hematite (Fe_2O_3); *ii.c)* magnetite (Fe_3O_4) or; *ii.d)*
186 pyrite (FeS_2). Their proportions ranged between 0 % and 50% (*Fe*, Fe_2O_3 or Fe_3O_4) or
187 between 0% and 15%, (FeS_2);

188 *iii)* cork powder (*Ck*), as source of organic carbon. Its percentage varied between 0 % and
189 5%;

190 *iv)* sodium carbonate, Na_2CO_3 , as flux. As above, its percentage ranged between 0 % and
191 5%.

192 Depending on the added iron phase type, the following types of aggregates have been
193 differentiated:

194 - *N.I.P-type*: manufactured without any iron phase and considered as “control aggregates”
195 (Table S1),

196 - *Fe-type*: manufactured with metallic iron (Table S2),

197 - *Fe₂O₃-type*: produced with hematite (Table S3),

198 - *Fe₃O₄-type*: manufactured with magnetite (Table S4),

199 - *FeS₂-type*: produced with pyrite (Table S5).

200 The main characteristics and/or properties of the four initial components, except for their
201 quantitative mineralogical analysis, were described in detail in Moreno-Maroto *et al.*
202 [10,11,12]. The chemical composition of the kaolinite-rich component is also
203 summarized in Table S6 (Supplementary Material).

204 In addition, these three works present the manufacturing process of the aggregates as well
205 as the methodology for their characterization that can be summarized as follows: After
206 the preparation and granulation of the mixtures, the dry aggregates were preheated for 2
207 minutes and heated for 10 minutes in a rotary kiln at the maximum temperature at which
208 the aggregates remained without sticking in the tube (T^a , between 1127°C and 1372°C).

209 **2.2. QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF THE MINERALOGICAL** 210 **PHASES AND THE AMORPHOUS MATERIAL IN THE RAW MATERIALS** 211 **AND THE ARTIFICIAL AGGREGATES**

212 The aggregates were previously milled into < 53 µm powder using a rotary agate mill
213 Retsch® RM 100. First, where possible, the separation between shell (external material,
214 *Ex.*) and core (internal material, *In.*) were mechanically separated. Then, a proportion of
215 25 wt% of *SRM 676a*, the standard reference material (an alumina powder with corundum
216 structure of high purity, 99.02% ± 1.11%, [13]) was added into each sample (raw
217 materials and aggregates) to be mixed by shaking at 30 cycles/s, for 1 min, in an agate-
218 container ball mill Restsch® MM 200 to ensure a proper homogeneity. Finally, X-ray
219 diffraction (*XRD*) analysis through a PANalytical® diffractometer X'Pert Pro model was
220 conducted. Both the mineral and the amorphous phases were quantitatively determined
221 relying on the Rietveld method [14,15,16], using the software PANalytical X'Pert
222 HighScore Plus. The refines variables were: scale factor, specimen displacement,
223 preferential orientation with spherical harmonics, unit cell parameters and profile
224 variables, using Finger, Cox, Jephcoat asymmetry type. The conditions were: 45 kV, 40
225 mA, CuKα radiation and a system of slits (soller – mask– divergence – antiscatter) of
226 0.04 rad – 15mm – 1/8° – 1/2°, 2-70° 2θ range, step size 0.0167°, counting time 100.330
227 s, with a X'celerator detector and a Bragg-Brentano HD module. The amorphous
228 percentage was determined by difference regarding the crystalline phase percentages
229 taking into account the exact proportion of *SRM 676a* added.

230 **2.3. TREATMENT OF RESULTS**

231 The mineralogical/phase composition results obtained after the application of the Rietveld
232 method are expressed in percentage by weight, that is, grams of a certain mineral/phase
233 present in 100 grams of raw material, $(Mineral\%)^{rw}_{Rtvld}$, or in 100 grams of artificial
234 aggregate, $(Phase\%)^{agr}_{Rtvld}$. It must be taken into account that 100 grams of raw material
235 will not produce 100 grams of aggregates since mass is lost on ignition, so the correct
236 comparison ought to be done between 100 grams of raw materials and 100-*LOI*(1+2)
237 grams of aggregates. For this, the percentages of a given mineral and the amorphous
238 material obtained for the aggregates after applying the Rietveld method must be
239 recalculated to $(Phase\%)^{agr}_{LOI}$ using the following formula:

$$240 \quad (Phase\%)^{agr}_{LOI} = [(Phase\%)^{agr}_{Rtvld} * (100-LOI(1+2))]/100 \text{ [Eq.1]},$$

241
242
243 where *LOI*(1+2) is the loss of mass due to ignition that this aggregate has had during its
244 entire firing process.

245 An independence contrast test was conducted to know if significant relationships exist
246 between the mineralogical composition of the raw materials and the phase composition
247 of the aggregates obtained from those raw materials. The software IBM SPSS Statistics
248 27 was used. First, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (*K-S*) test was applied to study the data
249 distribution. Based on those results, the Spearman's correlation coefficient (*rs*) test was
250 finally carried out to analyse the correlations for not requiring normal distribution.
251 Correlations have been considered significant at $p < 0.05$ and highly significant at $p < 0.01$
252 under bilateral analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. EVOLUTION OF THE MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION WITH THE HEATING TEMPERATURE

Tables 1 and 2 show the raw materials and aggregates mineralogical/phase composition, respectively. Based on the results of the mineralogical composition of the raw materials and on their proportions in the mixtures (Tables S1-S5), the proportions of each of the crystalline phases have been recalculated and presented in Tables 3-7 (*RM* rows). Also, the proportions of each crystalline phase detected in the aggregates have been recalculated using Eq. 1, obtaining the $(Phase\%)^{agr}_{LOI}$ values presented in Tables 3-7 (*AA* rows). Finally, *rs* values between the mineralogical phases of the raw materials and the phase composition of the aggregates are presented in Tables S7-S10 (Supplementary Material).

3.1.1. Kaolinite

Kaolinite, $Al_2(Si_2O_5)(OH)_4$, alternatively $Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, widely used in the manufacture of ceramics and bricks [17], is the main crystalline phase in the kaolinite-rich component (84.9%, Table 1). Its percentage in the raw materials varies between 34% and 84.9% but this crystalline phase dehydrates at around 450°C and is structurally altered above 800°C, so it is absent in the synthetic aggregates (Tables 3-7, *AA* rows), which have been fired between 1227°C and 1372°C.

Mullite has a nominal composition that can vary between $3Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2$ and $2Al_2O_3 \cdot SiO_2$ [17,18]. It can be produced by thermal decomposition of aluminosilicates such as kaolinite [19,20]. According to Pask and Tomsia [20], Liu *et al.* [21] and Sánchez-Soto *et al.* [22], among others, the thermal decomposition of kaolinite could be summarized as (Table 8):

Therefore, the mullite and cristobalite found in the aggregates are new crystalline phases formed from the thermal decomposition of the kaolinite present in all the raw materials (Table 9). This is supported statistically, since there are positive, highly significant correlations (at $p < 0.01$), between the initial percentage of kaolinite in the raw materials and the percentage of mullite in the aggregates ($rs = 0.94$, Tables S7; $rs = 0.95$, Table S8; $rs = 0.86$, Table S9). Also, the amorphous phase that has been found in the aggregates, especially in those where there is no cristobalite, would be a phase formed from the thermal decomposition of the kaolinite. This phase would have a composition rich in silicon oxide since it would be an amorphous silica phase that would not have yet transformed into α -cristobalite. Significant and negative correlations between the proportion of mullite and the proportion of amorphous phase in the aggregates ($rs = -0.82$, Table S7; $rs = -0.76$, Table S8; $rs = -0.91$, Table S9; $rs = -0.66$, Table S10) are observed which could indicate that there is new formation of mullite (from kaolinite) to the detriment of the new formation of amorphous phase and *vice versa*.

3.1.2. Quartz

The proportion of quartz, SiO_2 , in the raw material ranges between 5% and 12.6% (Tables 3-7, *RM* rows). After firing, quartz is still present in most of the aggregates, but always in lower percentages than in the starting materials (0.4%-5.5%, Tables 3-7, *AA* rows), so its presence in the artificial aggregates is considered as a relic of the quartz of the raw materials.

It could be expected that the decrease in the percentage of quartz in the aggregates will lead to an increase in the presence of the more important SiO_2 polymorphs stable at high temperatures, such as cristobalite, as it has been observed in some of the aggregates manufactured with any of the phases of iron as well as in previous works where quartz is

part of the raw materials of lightweight aggregates [23]. In turn, this does not occur in the aggregates manufactured without any phase of iron (Table 3). It is in accordance with another previous study, where cristobalite was not found as a high-temperature phase in any fired sample using quartz-bearing raw materials [24]. In the *N.I.P.-type* aggregates, the “lost quartz” has become part of the amorphous phase since no other crystalline phase (with the exception of mullite, which is expected to come from kaolinite) has been found. As Wei and Ko [9] reported, the formation of an aggregate glassy surface is related with the almost complete disappearance of quartz after LWAs sintering.

3.1.3. *Illite*

The proportion of illite, $K_{1.5-1.0}Al_4(Si_{6.5-7.0}Al_{1.5-1.0}O_{20})(OH)_4$, ranges from 1% up to 2.5% in the raw materials while it is not found in any of the aggregates (Tables 3-7, *AA* rows). This is due to decomposition of illite above 850-950°C [17,25]. Previous studies [26,27] have shown that with the increase in temperature up to about 1100°C, Si in the layers is transformed into the amorphous state. Meanwhile, mullite forms at around 1100°C and remarkably increases at 1200 °C, so it could be established that the initial illite could have become part of the amorphous material of the aggregate and/or have acted as precursor of the mullite formation [27] (Table 9).

3.1.4. *Metallic iron*

Metallic iron, Fe, is part of the raw materials in one of the types of artificial aggregates, *Fe-type* (Tables S2 and 4), with proportions ranging from 0% to 50%. After heating, metallic iron is found in all the aggregates in percentages varying between 0.1% and 2.2% (Table 4, *AA* rows). This proportion is always lower than the metallic iron proportion in the raw materials, being a relic of the initial composition. Proof of this is the high positive correlation that exists between the percentage of metallic iron in the raw materials and the percentage of metallic iron found in the aggregates ($r_s=0.93$, Table S7). Since the metallic iron volatilization is not possible given its high boiling point and additionally, hematite, magnetite, hercynite and/or fayalite have not been found in the “control aggregates” but they have been found in the *Fe-type* aggregates, the presence of these new crystalline phases could be associated with the existence of metallic iron in the raw material.

First, iron is normally present as Fe^{2+} or Fe^{3+} in oxides such as magnetite, Fe_3O_4 , or hematite, Fe_2O_3 [28]. Moreover, significant and positive correlations have been found between the percentage of metallic iron in the raw materials and the percentage of hematite ($r_s=0.73$) and/or magnetite ($r_s=0.64$) in the aggregates, being possible to establish that their formation is due to the oxidation of metallic iron (Table 9). This is in accordance with Moreno-Maroto *et al.* [12], where a lower total mass loss than that observed during preheating was attributed to the iron gaining mass through oxidation in the kiln atmosphere, giving rise to Fe_3O_4 and/or Fe_2O_3 .

Secondly, when kaolinite transforms thermally, it can crystallize in the form of spinel (hercynite, $FeAl_2O_4$, in this case) when reacts with iron [29,30]. Also, metallic iron could oxidise to FeO and reacts with kaolinite decomposed to mullite to form Fe_2SiO_4 (fayalite), $FeAl_2O_4$ (hercynite) and $FeSiO_3$ (ferrosilite) [31], according to [32,33] (Table 8):

As can be seen, the reaction pathways of hercynite ($FeAl_2O_4$) and fayalite (Fe_2SiO_4) from FeO and mullite can be diverse, reactions that in turn are dependent on factors such as temperature, H_2/H_2O ratio or P_{O_2} [34].

In addition, a proportion of the initial metallic iron must have become part of the mullite structure and/or the composition of the amorphous material, since there are *Fe-type* aggregates that do not have hematite, magnetite, hercynite nor fayalite. Fe³⁺ may appreciably replace Al in the mullite structure with up to almost 6% Fe₂O₃ [17]. Also, positive correlation has been observed between the percentage of metallic iron in the raw materials and the percentage of amorphous phase in the aggregates (*rs*=0.77, Table S7). Figure 1 shows the graphic representation of the initial metallic iron percentage (X axis) vs the percentage of amorphous phase found in the aggregates once they have been fired (Y axis). As shown, an upward trend can be seen, adjusting to the following first-degree equation (coefficient of determination, *R*²=0.94):

$$Am. Ph._2 = 0.52 (Fe_1) + 48.66 \text{ [Eq. 2]}$$

Where *Am. Ph.₂* is the percentage of amorphous phase in the aggregates manufactured with an initial percentage of metallic iron, *Fe₁*.

3.1.5. Hematite

The percentage of hematite, Fe₂O₃, in the raw material varies from 18.3% up to 50% (Table 5, *RM* rows). After firing, it decreases in all cases, ranging from 4.9% to 25.8% (Table 5, *AA* rows).

Hematite can reduce to magnetite using thermal treatment and in the presence of CO-CO₂, H₂-H₂O, N₂ and/or CH₄ gas mixtures [35]. This reduction would be subject to reactions such as (Table 8):

The presence of magnetite in artificial aggregates manufactured from raw materials containing hematite is consistent with previous studies, such as the work of Serry *et al.* [23].

Clinopyroxenes, where iron can form part of their crystalline structure [17], have been found in some of the aggregates manufactured with hematite (Table 5). Taking into account the main chemical elements that make up pyroxenes (Si, Al and O) and that clinopyroxenes do not appear in the *N.I.P*-type nor in *Fe-type* aggregates, it can be established that clinopyroxene formation is most likely due to reactions between kaolinite and hematite. This is in agreement with that reported by Han *et al.* [31] showing that ferrosilite was precipitated during the reaction of mullite and hematite reduced to FeO.

Hercynite is also a new crystalline phase produced in the *Fe₂O₃*-type aggregate (Table 5). Its presence can be justified along the same lines as in *Fe-type* aggregates. In this case, first, the reduction of hematite to FeO is necessary (Fe₂O₃ → 2FeO + ½ O₂, Rc. 8), which has been considered one of the responsible of the gas phase generation in the production of lightweight aggregates [23,36]. Then, the resulting FeO could react with the product of the kaolinite thermal decomposition, mullite. Hercynite with high purity can be synthesized using aluminium oxide and hematite as raw material with SiO₂ addition [37]. A percentage of the iron that composes the initial hematite must have become part of the mullite structure and/or the composition of the amorphous material (Table 9). Chen *et al.*, [37] showed that, in addition to the neoformation of hercynite, the generation of an amorphous phase mainly composed of Si, Fe, Al and O from hematite, Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ bearing raw materials is possible.

3.1.6. Magnetite

The proportion of magnetite, Fe²⁺Fe³⁺₂O₄, decreases during aggregate formation with respect to that of the raw materials (Table 6). Since a significant correlation exists between the magnetite percentage in the aggregates and that in the raw materials (*rs*=0.94, Table S9), it can be considered as a residual magnetite from raw materials.

403 Magnetite can be oxidized to hematite using thermal treatment and in presence of
404 oxidizing gases [38] according to (Table 8):

406 Hematite has been detected in most of the aggregates manufactured with magnetite (Table
407 6) and, additionally, there is a significant correlation between these two mineralogical
408 phases ($r_s=0.75$, Table S9), so part of the initial magnetite has oxidized producing the
409 hematite found in the aggregates. The hematite formation is responsible for the reddish
410 colour of the LWA shell where it appears [11].

411 Correlation has also been found between the magnetite in the raw materials and the
412 hercynite in the aggregates (Table S9) so it is possible that the latter has been formed due
413 to the presence of magnetite in the raw materials following the same mechanism that
414 hercynite formed from metallic iron and/or hematite. This is in accordance with studies
415 where hercynite was synthesized using Al and magnetite, in an argon atmosphere [39]. A
416 reaction that could represent the formation of hercynite is [40] (Table 8):

418 where the Fe^0 presence as well as the existence of an argon atmosphere could indicate that
419 hercynite formation is favoured by reducing environments.

420 There is one artificial aggregate manufactured with magnetite that contains fayalite
421 (Table 6). This would be in accordance with that has already been developed for the
422 formation of fayalite from metallic iron. Li *et al.* [41] showed that the content
423 of fayalite increased while the magnetite decreased after its reduction by petro-diesel and
424 biodiesel. The role of these organic compounds would be similar to that of the cork used
425 in this work: to reduce magnetite to fayalite. Furthermore, this aggregate is manufactured
426 with the highest percentage of *Ck*.

427 Therefore, depending on the type of atmosphere in the aggregate, the formation of
428 hematite (oxidizing environments) will be favoured to the detriment of that of hercynite
429 and/or fayalite (reducing environments) and *vice versa*. Furthermore, this would be
430 clearly reflected in Table 6, where the percentage of hematite is always higher in the
431 external material than in the internal, while the percentage of hercynite and fayalite is
432 always higher in the internal than in the external.

433 There is a significant positive correlation between the percentage of magnetite in the raw
434 materials and the percentage of amorphous material in the aggregates ($r_s=0.69$, Table S9),
435 suggesting that part of the raw materials' magnetite could have become part of the
436 amorphous material of the aggregate (Table 9).

437 **3.1.7. Pyrite rich raw material**

438 Pyrite, FeS_2 , is the main crystalline phase in the FeS_2 raw material (78.6%, Table 1). Its
439 percentage in the mixtures varies between 1.4% and 11.8% (Table 7, *RM* rows) but it is
440 not detected in any of the aggregates (Table 7, *AA* rows) since they have been subjected
441 to temperatures between 1200 and 1345°C. Pyrite thermal decomposition is a known
442 process, although it is very complex and depending on many factors that affect
443 the decomposition reactions [42,43]. The thermal decomposition pyrite begins to
444 transform into monoclinic pyrrhotite at 500–600°C, and afterwards, to hexagonal
445 pyrrhotite at 700–800°C; at 900°C, more stable FeS is formed. At the temperatures applied
446 here it is reasonable to expect none of the original pyrite to remain.

447 There are aggregates made with pyrite that have hematite and/or troilite (FeS) (Table 7),
448 phases which were not found in the control aggregates (Table 3). Additionally, there are
449 significant positive correlation between the pyrite percentage in the raw materials and the
450 troilite percentages in the aggregates (Table S10). These two results suggest that pyrite in
451 the raw materials has been transformed to hematite and/or troilite in the aggregates (Table
452 9). Aracena and Jerez [44] show that the pyrite oxidation first produces an intermediate

453 compound, pyrrhotite (Fe_7S_8 or $\text{Fe}_{(1-x)}\text{S}$), which is later oxidized to generate hematite,
454 according to the following reactions (Table 8):

457 Also, pyrite thermal decomposition in a nitrogen atmosphere [45] and in an argon
458 atmosphere [46] has been described as follows: pyrite \rightarrow pyrrhotite \rightarrow troilite. The
459 decomposition/reduction of pyrite under argon may follow the reactions [47]:

462 Hercynite is also a newly formed crystalline phase in the FeS_2 -type aggregate (30- FeS_2 ,
463 Table 7), justified as in the Fe -, Fe_2O_3 - and Fe_3O_4 -type aggregates cases. Liu *et al.* [48]
464 showed that pyrite was gradually transformed into pyrrhotite. Then, in the reduction
465 stage, this pyrrhotite was converted into magnetite and subsequently changed to FeO ,
466 which reacted with Al_2O_3 (from kaolinite) to produce hercynite above 1000 °C.

467 Therefore, depending on the type of atmosphere that prevails during aggregate synthesis
468 (oxidizing or reducing), the pyrite of the raw materials will be transformed into hematite
469 in oxidizing atmospheres and/or troilite or hercynite in reducing conditions.

470 As metallic iron, hematite and magnetite, it can be established that part of the raw
471 materials' pyrite could have been accommodated in the mullite structure and/or
472 partitioned into the composition of the amorphous material.

473 **3.1.8. Cork powder**

474 The cork powder used in the aggregate manufacturing, *Ck*, does not have any
475 mineralogical phase; it is composed by 100% amorphous phase. It has been added to all
476 the types of aggregates in proportion between 0% and 5%. After the firing process, it is
477 expected that approximately the 100% of cork would be lost during the heating process
478 (Table 9), as it is shown by the DTA-TG graph in Moreno-Maroto *et al.* [10]. Cork
479 combustion could give rise to several hypothetical "scenarios" during the manufacture of
480 aggregates:

481 *i)* in presence of excess oxygen, the complete combustion of the cork is produced
482 according to this general reaction:

484 maintaining an oxidizing atmosphere inside the rotary kiln and promoting the formation
485 of minerals that require this type of atmosphere, such as hematite or magnetite from
486 metallic iron.

487 *ii)* in low oxygen conditions, a situation that can occur in the core of the aggregates, where
488 the incomplete combustion of the cork could be produced according to the general
489 reaction:

492 giving rise to CO that can favour the reduction of compounds such as hematite
493 transformed to magnetite or/and from magnetite to fayalite. In addition, some carbon may
494 remain unburned [10,11,12] and other gases such as H_2 or N_2 , can produce an even more
495 reducing atmosphere increasing the range of redox conditions that can occur inside the
496 aggregates. Thus, unburned carbon particles could react directly with Fe_2O_3 or Fe_3O_4 [49]
497 according to:

500 *iii)* mixed conditions: in the interior of aggregates where cork has been added, CO_2
501 (generated from Rcs. 15 or 16) could be reduced by unburned carbon according to [50]:

generating a change in the type of redox environment of the aggregate from oxidizing (CO₂ presence) to reducing (CO presence).

Therefore, cork can play an important role in controlling mineral speciation as a major influence on redox chemistry.

3.1.9. Natrite

Natrite, Na₂CO₃, has been added as raw material to all the types of aggregates in proportions ranging between 0% and 5 %. After heating, it has not been detected in any of the aggregates (Tables 3-7) as this mineral decomposes between 800-900°C (lower than *T^o*) according to the reaction [51] (Table 8):

CO₂ can be released directly, forming part of *LOI (I+2)*, especially in the presence of an oxidizing atmosphere. Nevertheless, CO₂ could be reduced in the presence of other compounds, such as unburned carbon (Rc. 19) and generate an even more reducing atmosphere inside the aggregates (reacting to produce CO), favouring the formation of minerals that require this type of atmosphere. Therefore, defining the type of atmosphere that could be generated with the addition of Na₂CO₃ would be very complex, largely depending on reactions of carbon derived from the combustion of cork.

Na₂O can react with silicates (present in the raw materials) at high temperatures according to [51] (Table 8):

Thus, the composition of the final products will be dependent on the temperature, the silicate proportion [52] and the other elements that are present in the silicates, such as aluminium and iron.

Evidence of the incorporation of Na into the structure of newly formed crystalline phases is the presence of nepheline ((Na,K)AlSiO₄) in some of the aggregates studied (Table 7). It could be in accordance with previous works, where nepheline has been synthesized from raw kaolinite and a NaOH solution by an alkali-hydrothermal induced transformation process [53].

Additionally, Na could form part of the crystalline structure of the produced clinopyroxenes (Tables 5 and 6) since Na can be incorporated in the aegirite (NaFe³⁺Si₂O₆) solid solution series of pyroxenes [17] as well as the amorphous phase of the aggregates without Na-bearing crystalline phases as the *N.I.P*-type and *Fe-type* aggregates (Table 3 and 4, cases where Na₂CO₃ has been added).

3.2. EFFECT OF THE TYPE OF INITIAL IRON PHASE, THE PROPORTION OF EACH RAW MATERIAL COMPONENT AND THE ATMOSPHERE TYPE ON THE AGGREGATES PHASE COMPOSITION

3.2.1. Magnetite

In the aggregates manufactured with hematite as raw material, magnetite has been only found in one of the aggregates studied, specifically in *36-Fe₂O₃* (Table 5). Although its presence in these aggregates is largely due to the addition of an iron phase to the raw materials, the magnetite quantity in the aggregates is not dependent on the percentage of hematite added, so its presence would be further determined due to other factors. In fact, as well as *36-Fe₂O₃*, there are another five aggregates (*27-Fe₂O₃*, *29-Fe₂O₃*, *32-Fe₂O₃*, *33-Fe₂O₃*, and *Op-Fe₂O₃*) with the highest percentage of initial hematite (50%) that do not have magnetite. The main difference between these five aggregates and *36-Fe₂O₃* is that the last has been manufactured with the highest proportion of Na₂CO₃ (5%) and the highest proportion of cork powder (5%) whose decomposition could give rise to a more favourable environment for the reduction of hematite to magnetite.

553 **3.2.2. Mullite, cristobalite and the amorphous phase**

1 554 When Fe, Fe₂O₃ or Fe₃O₄ are added as raw material, it is observed that the higher the
2 555 proportion of kaolinite in the raw materials, the greater the proportion of mullite in the
3 556 aggregates. Despite this, although all aggregates have been manufactured with kaolinite,
4 557 there are some aggregates where mullite is not detected. Rc. 1 (Table 8) clearly reflects
5 558 that the mullite formation could be diminished by γ -alumina or aluminium-silicon spinel
6 559 formation. As it can be seen, the *Fe-type* and *Fe₃O₄-type* aggregates present an increased
7 560 number of samples with newly formed hercynite which, in turn, present a significant and
8 561 negative correlation with the percentage of mullite in the aggregates (Tables S7 and S9)
9 562 so when mullite does not appear in the aggregate, this could be due to the formation of
10 563 hercynite has occurred instead or because the neo formed mullite has reacted with FeO
11 564 according to Rc. 3 and 4 (Table 8). Contrary to *Fe-type*, *Fe₂O₃-type* and *Fe₃O₄-type*
12 565 aggregates, when FeS₂ is the added iron phase, no significant correlation is observed
13 566 between the percentage of kaolinite in the raw materials and the percentage of mullite
14 567 generated in the aggregates. Although the newly formed mullite is necessarily due to the
15 568 presence of kaolinite in the raw materials, the percentage of kaolinite is not determinative
16 569 of the extent of mullite formation in the aggregates and therefore other factors will
17 570 additionally influence mullite formation.

18 571 Cristobalite appears in the four types of aggregates with some iron phase but it is not
19 572 present in the *N.I.P-type* aggregates, so its presence would be promoted by the addition
20 573 of an iron phase as raw material [54]. In relation to this, it has been shown that cristobalite
21 574 does not crystallize in the absence of ferrous ion below 1200°C but it does, as along with
22 575 fayalite, when silica gel is mixed with ferrous oxalate in a mildly reducing atmosphere
23 576 and heated at 1100 °C [55]. Despite this, the cristobalite percentage does not show any
24 577 correlation with the percentage of the added iron phase, so the amount of cristobalite
25 578 seems more dependent on some other factors. In three of the four types of aggregates (*Fe-*
26 579 *, Fe₂O₃- and FeS₂-types*), the percentage of cristobalite presents a significant and negative
27 580 correlation with the percentage of natrite (Tables S7, S8 and S10), where the cristobalite
28 581 percentage is higher in those cases where natrite has not been added, or where its
29 582 proportion is lower (no more than 1.25%). The reaction between natrite and the Si present
30 583 in the raw material could be possible (Rcs. 20 and 21) suppressing cristobalite formation.
31 584 Additionally, the absence of cristobalite in the aggregates could be due to the reaction of
32 585 the product of Rc.21, Na₂SiO₃(Table 8), with the newly formed cristobalite according to
33 586 Solihin *et al.*, [56]: they reported the formation of a geopolymer (amorphous) from
34 587 a reaction among cristobalite, disodium metasilicate (Na₂SiO₃) and amorphous
35 588 aluminium silicates.

36 589 The percentage of amorphous phase found in the aggregates would be influenced
37 590 positively by the amount of Fe, Fe₂O₃ and/or Fe₃O₄ added, since aggregates with a higher
38 591 percentage of these iron-bearing compounds as raw materials present a higher proportion
39 592 of amorphous material than those with a lower proportion. This is supported statistically
40 593 (Tables S7-S9). On the contrary, when the added iron phase is pyrite, there is no
41 594 significant correlation between the percentage of this mineral and the percentage of the
42 595 amorphous phase in the aggregates (Table S10).

43 596 **3.2.3. Hercynite, fayalite and clinopyroxenes**

44 597 It has been demonstrated that, under controlled atmosphere and temperature system, the
45 598 SiO₂ addition to Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ as raw materials promotes the sintering and crystal
46 599 growth of hercynite by the peritectic reaction [37]. In this work, it has been found that the
47 600 *Fe-* and *Fe₃O₄-type* aggregates made with the highest proportion of kaolinite, quartz and
48 601 illite do not form hercynite, while those manufactured with the smallest proportion have
49 602 hercynite (Tables 4 and 6).

603 The presence of fayalite in *Fe*-type and/or *Fe₃O₄*-type aggregates is in agreement with the
604 rest of the phase composition of the aggregates since fayalite is a type of olivine, which
605 is incompatible with the presence of quartz and cristobalite at equilibrium [57] and
606 precisely, *30-Fe* and *35-Fe₃O₄* are the only aggregates that do not contain quartz or
607 cristobalite.

608 In the aggregates where hematite has been added, when clinopyroxenes are found in high
609 abundance, the amount of cork in the raw materials is relatively high (3.75%-5.0%). This
610 fact could indicate that the thermal decomposition of this compound, together with the
611 presence of kaolinite and hematite, would favour the formation of this group of minerals.
612 Considering Table 5, it can be seen that the highest proportions occur in the core of two
613 aggregates, *19-Fe₂O₃(In)* (6.3%) and *32-Fe₂O₃(In)* (5.2%), indicating that they may need
614 a reducing atmosphere, which could be seen even more marked by the incomplete
615 combustion of cork in the core.

616 In the aggregates where magnetite has been added, it is possible to observe that the
617 hematite appears mainly in the external material of the aggregates and when it does in the
618 core, it is always in a much smaller proportion than in the shell (Table 6). Clinopyroxenes
619 are also detected in the external material of the aggregates and they never appear in the
620 internal material (Table 6) indicating the need for oxidizing atmosphere for hematite and
621 clinopyroxenes formation from magnetite. This is in agreement with previous works
622 where the formation of ferrosilite (FeSiO₃) from the oxidation of fayalite is reported [58].
623 In this type of aggregate, the presence of fayalite has been detected in some of them, but
624 without clinopyroxenes, so it would support the idea of the formation of clinopyroxenes
625 and fayalite. The FeSiO₃ formation process is governed by the following reactions (Table
626 8):

630 The latter is different from what has been developed for the formation of clinopyroxenes
631 from hematite: in that case, their formation is favoured by a reducing atmosphere.
632 Therefore, it can be established that depending on whether the production of
633 clinopyroxenes is from hematite or magnetite, it will be influenced by a reducing or
634 oxidizing environment, respectively.

635 By comparison, hercynite and fayalite are always detected in higher proportion in the
636 internal material of the aggregates than in the external material, appearing only in the
637 aggregate core in some cases (Table 6) indicating therefore, the need for reducing
638 conditions for hercynite and fayalite formation from magnetite. The main reason is that
639 the valence state of iron in hercynite and fayalite is ferrous (Fe²⁺), while generally the
640 stable valence of iron in contact with atmospheric oxygen is trivalent – ferric iron [37].

641 **3.2.4. Troilite and nepheline**

642 The fact that troilite appears in *33-FeS₂(In)* and not in *33-FeS₂(Ex)* would confirm the
643 need for a reducing atmosphere for its formation from the pyrite.

644 Nepheline is present only in aggregates where the percentage of natrite in the raw
645 materials is the highest (5%). Despite this, there are aggregates with this proportion of
646 sodium that do not have nepheline so its formation would additionally require other
647 atmospheric conditions [59]. In this case it would be oxidizing since the highest
648 proportion of nepheline (30.8%) is detected in the external material of an aggregate, *33-*
649 *FeS₂(Ex)*, and not in the core of this aggregate (Table 7).

653 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

654 Based on the results obtained and in their statistical analysis, the following conclusions
655 can be established:

- 656 i) Regardless of the iron phase added as raw material, iron could become part of the
657 structure of mullite and the amorphous phase in the aggregates. Additionally, it
658 could become part of the crystalline structure of one or several of the following
659 reaction products depending on the iron-bearing raw material:
660 a. hematite, magnetite, hercynite and/or fayalite, if metallic iron is added;
661 b. magnetite, hercynite and/or clinopyroxenes, if hematite is added;
662 c. hematite, hercynite, fayalite and/or clinopyroxenes, if magnetite is added;
663 d. hematite, hercynite and/or troilite, if pyrite is added.
664 Also, the iron phases added, except pyrite, remain as relics in the aggregates.
665 ii) The Na₂CO₃ thermal decomposition contributes to the formation of nepheline and
666 amorphous material in some artificial aggregates. Additionally, its addition, like
667 that of cork, plays an important role in the minerals formation since their thermal
668 decomposition can give rise to a wide range of conditions: oxidizing, reducing or
669 both atmospheres depending on whether it is the external or internal zone of the
670 aggregates. It seems likely that the sodium carbonate (Mp 851 °C) melt acts as a
671 flux, dissolving other components in the system.
672 iii) Cristobalite formation from the kaolinite-rich component would be indirectly
673 promoted by the addition of an iron phase as raw material but, in turn, would be
674 inhibited, also indirectly, by the addition of Na₂CO₃.
675 iv) The presence and abundance of hematite, magnetite, hercynite, fayalite and
676 clinopyroxenes are conditioned by the initial iron phase and by the type of
677 atmosphere (oxidizing or reducing) in the aggregates.
678 v) The percentage of troilite in the aggregates increases with the increase in pyrite in
679 the raw materials, where the reaction atmosphere is reducing
680 vi) The formation of nepheline requires, in addition to high percentages of natrite, an
681 oxidizing atmosphere.
682 vii) The percentage of the amorphous phase found in the aggregates is positively
683 influenced by the amount of Fe, Fe₂O₃, or Fe₃O₄ added as raw material.
684

685 Additionally, the following general conclusions can be also postulated:

- 686 - Both a qualitative and quantitative comparison of the phase assemblage before and
687 after heating can be made when a precise identification of the different phases has been
688 carried out and subsequently the Rietveld method has been applied for the quantification
689 of the different phases.
690 - To make a correct quantitative comparison of the mineralogical evolution of these
691 systems during sintering, it is extremely important to take into account the loss on ignition
692 suffered by the aggregates during the firing process. Specifically, the *LOI (I+2)* values
693 are critical factors in interpretation of the synthesis of artificial aggregates.
694 Finally, it can be established that all the results and discussions presented in this work can
695 serve as the basis for future studies of great importance, such as determining the effect
696 that the phase composition of the aggregates has on their technological properties. This
697 in turn, allows optimisation of aggregate synthesis from a wide range of starting materials.
698

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704

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720 **References**

- 721 [1] EN-13055-1, Lightweight aggregates. Part 1: Lightweight aggregates for concrete,
722 mortar and grout, European Committee for Standardization, 2002.
- 723 [2] González-Corrochano, B., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Rodríguez, L., Pérez Lorenzo, A.,
724 Fernández Torio, M., Tejado Ramos, J.J., Covinos, M.D., Muro, C., Effect heating dwell
725 time has on the retention of heavy metals in the structure of lightweight aggregates
726 manufactured from wastes, *Environ. Technol.* 39 (2018) 2511-2523.
727 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2017.1358768>
- 728 [3] De'Genaro, R., Cappelletti, P., Cerri, G., De'Genaro, M., Dondi, M., Langella, A.,
729 Zeolitic tuffs as raw materials for lightweight aggregates, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 25 (2004) 71-
730 81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2003.08.005>
- 731 [4] Riley, C.M., Relation of chemical properties to the bloating of clays, *J. Am. Ceram.*
732 *Soc.*, 34 (1951), 121-128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1951.tb11619.x>
- 733 [5] Bilqees, R., Naeem, P., Khan, T., Junaid, M.M., Engineering tests of aggregate from
734 lightweight expanded slate of Manki Formation, *J. Himal. Earth Sci.* 44 (2011) 53-60.
- 735 [6] Lee, K.G, Bloating mechanism for coal ash with iron oxide, *J. Korean Cryst. Growth*
736 *Cryst. Technol.* 24 (2014) 77-83. <https://doi.org/10.6111/JKCGCT.2014.24.2.077>
- 737 [7] Cubaud, U.C., Murat, M., Fabricación industrial de arcilla expandida, *Materiales de*
738 *Construcción* 19 (1969) 5-16. <http://materconstrucc.revistas.csic.es>
- 739 [8] Yang, C., Cui, C., Qin, J., Recycling of low-silicon iron tailings in the production of
740 lightweight aggregates, *Ceram. Int.* 41 (2015) 1213-1221.
741 <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2014.09.050>
- 742 [9] Wei, Y-L., Ko, G-W., Recycling steel wastewater sludges as raw materials for
743 preparing lightweight aggregates, *J. Cleaner Prod.* 165 (2017) 905-916.
744 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.07.186>
- 745 [10] Moreno-Maroto, J.M., Cobo-Ceacero, C.J., Conde-Sánchez, A., Martínez-
746 Rodríguez, A.M., González-Corrochano, B., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Uceda-Rodríguez, M.,
747 López, A.B., Martínez-García, C., Cotes-Palomino, T., Can statistical methods optimize
748 complex multicomponent mixtures for sintering ceramic granular materials? A case of
749 success with synthetic aggregates, *Ceram. Int.* 49 (2023) 24195-24206.
750 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.09.220>

- 751 [11] Moreno-Maroto, J.M., Cobo-Ceacero, C.J., Martínez-Rodríguez, A.M., Conde-
752 Sánchez, A., González-Corrochano, B., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Uceda-Rodríguez, M.,
753 López, A.B., Martínez-García, C., Cotes-Palomino, T., Study of the synergistic impact of
754 Fe₃O₄, Na₂CO₃ and organic C on kaolin-based lightweight aggregates by a DOE (Mixture
755 Experiments) approach. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 403 (2023) 133152.
756 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133152>
- 757 [12] Moreno-Maroto, J.M., González-Corrochano, B., Martínez-Rodríguez, A.M.,
758 Conde-Sánchez, A., Cobo-Ceacero, C.J., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Uceda-Rodríguez, M.,
759 López, A.B., Martínez-García, C., Cotes-Palomino, T., Analyzing the role of Fe⁰ and Fe³⁺
760 in the formation of expanded clay aggregates, *Mater.*, 16 (2023) 5623.
761 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16165623>
- 762 [13] NIST, Certificate of Analysis. Standard Reference Material 676a. Alumina Powder
763 for Quantitative Analysis by X-ray Diffraction, National Institute of Standards and
764 Technology, 2012.
- 765 [14] Bish, D.L., Post, J.E., Quantitative mineralogical analysis using the Rietveld full
766 pattern fitting method, *Am. Mineral.* 78 (1993) 932-940.
- 767 [15] De la Torre, A.G., Bruque, S., Aranda, M.A.G., Rietveld quantitative amorphous
768 content analyses, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 34 (2001) 196-202.
769 <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889801002485>
- 770 [16] Moreno-Maroto, J.M., González-Corrochano, B., Alonso-Azcárate, J., Rodríguez,
771 L., Acosta, A., Assessment of crystalline phase changes and glass formation by Rietveld-
772 XRD method on ceramic lightweight aggregates sintered from mineral and polymeric
773 wastes, *Ceram. Int.* 44 (2018) 11840-11851.
774 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.03.274>
- 775 [17] Deer, W.A., Howie, R.A., Zussman, J., An introduction to the rock-forming
776 minerals. Mineralogical Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 2013.
777 <https://doi.org/10.1180/DHZ>
- 778 [18] Schneider, H., Okada, K., Pask, J.A., Mullite and Mullite Ceramics, Wiley,
779 Chichester, UK, 1994.
- 780 [19] Liu, K.C., Thomas, G., Caballero, A., Moya, J.S., de Aza, S., Time-temperature
781 transformation curves for kaolinite- α -alumina, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 77 (1994) 1545-1552.
782 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1994.tb09755.x>
- 783 [20] Pask, J.A., Tomsia, A.P., Formation of mullite from sol-gel mixtures and kaolinite,
784 *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 74 (1991) 2367-2373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1991.tb06770.x>
- 785
786 [21] Liu, X.X., Liu, X.W., Hu, Y.H, Investigation on the thermal behaviour and
787 decomposition kinetics of kaolinite, *Clay Miner.* 50 (2015) 199-209.
788 <https://doi.org/10.1180/claymin.2015.050.2.04>
- 789 [22] Sánchez-Soto, P.J., Eliche-Quesada, D., Martínez-Martínez, S., Pérez-Villarejo, L.,
790 Garzón, E., Study of a waste kaolin as raw material for mullite ceramics and mullite
791 refractories by reaction sintering, *Mater.* 15 (2022), 583.
792 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15020583>
- 793 [23] Serry, M.A., Hegab, O.A, Abd El-Wahed, A.G., Egyptian smectite-rich clay for
794 lightweight and heavy clay products, *Period. Mineral.* 84 (2015) 351-371.
795 <https://doi.org/10.2451/2015PM0018>
- 796 [24] Jordán, M.M., Meseguer, S., Pardo, F., Montero, M.A., High-temperature mineral
797 formation after firing clay materials associated with mined coal in Teruel (Spain), *Appl.*
798 *Science-Basel* 10 (2020) 3114. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10093114>

- 799 [25] McConville, C.J, Lee, W.E., Microstructural development of firing illite and smectite
800 clays compared with that in kaolinite. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 88 (2005), 2267-2276.
801 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-2916.2005.00390.x>
- 802 [26] Jiang, T., Cui, Z.X., Li, G.H., Fan, X.H., Huang, Z.C., Qui, G.Z., Desilication from
803 illite by thermochemical activation. *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China* 14 (2004), 1000-
804 1005.
- 805 [27] Sedmale, G., Sperberga, I., Sedmalis, U., Valancius, Z., Formation of high-
806 temperature crystalline phases in ceramic from illite clay and dolomite, *J. Eur. Ceram.*
807 *Soc.* 26 (2006), 3351-3355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2005.10.012>
- 808 [28] Klein, C., Hurlbut, C.S., *Manual de Mineralogía*, Vol. II. Basado en la obra de J.D.
809 Dana., fourth ed., Reverté, S.A., Barcelona, España, 1997.
- 810 [29] Laita, E., Bauluz, B., Mayayo, M.J., Yuste, A., Mineral and textural transformations
811 in mixtures of Al-rich and Al-K-rich clays with firing: refractory potential of the fired
812 products. *Ceram. Int.* 47 (2021) 14527-14539.
813 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.02.032>
- 814 [30] Segnit, E. R. and Gelb, T. Metastable quartz-type structures formed from kaolinite
815 by solid state re-action. *Am. Min.* 57 (1972) 1505-1514.
- 816 [31] Han, K.B., Graser, J., Robert, C.J., de Mendoca, L.M., McLennan, J., Sparks, T.D.,
817 Synthesis and microstructural evolution in iron oxide kaolinite based proppant as a
818 function of reducing atmosphere, sintering conditions, and composition. *Ceram. Int.* 44
819 (2018) 9976-9983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.03.047>
- 820 [32] Pillay, T., D'entremont, J., Chipman, J., Stability of hercynite at high temperatures,
821 *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 43 (1960) 583-585. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1960.tb13620>.
- 822 [33] Zhou, Q., Li, C., Li, X., Peng, Z., Liu, G., Qi, T., Reaction behavior of ferric oxide
823 in system $Fe_2O_3-SiO_2-Al_2O_3$ during reductive sintering process, *Trans. Nonferrous Met.*
824 *Soc. China* 26 (2016) 842-848. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326\(16\)64175-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326(16)64175-4)
- 825 [34] Kobayashi, Y., Ohira, O., Satch, T., Compositions for strengthening porcelain bodies
826 in alumina-feldspar-kaolin system, *Br. Ceram. Trans.* 93 (1994) 49-52
- 827 [35] Janowski, J., Sadowski, A., Kinetics of low temperature reduction of hematite to
828 magnetite. *Ironmak. Steelmak.* 23 (1996), 479-485.
- 829 [36] Balapour, M., Rao, R., Garboczi, E.J., Spatari, S., Hsuan, Y.G., Billen, P., Farnam,
830 Y., Thermochemical principles of the production of lightweight aggregates from waste
831 coal bottom ash, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 104 (2021) 613-634.
832 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jace.17458>
- 833 [37] Chen J.H., Yan, M.W., Su, J.D., Li, B., Sun, J.L., Chou, K.C., Hou, X.M., Effect of
834 SiO_2 addition on the synthesis of hercynite with high purity, *J. Ceram. Soc. Japan* 123
835 (2015) 595-600. <https://doi.org/10.2109/jcersj2.123.595>
- 836 [38] Forsmo, S.P.E., Forsmo, S.E., Samskog, P.O., Bjorkman, B.M.T., Mechanisms in
837 oxidation and sintering of magnetite iron ore green pellets, *Powder Technol.*, 183 (2008),
838 247-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2007.07.032>
- 839 [39] Botta, P.M., Aglietti, E. F., López, J.M.P., Mechanochemical synthesis of hercynite.
840 *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 76 (2002), 104-109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0254-0584\(01\)00505-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0254-0584(01)00505-3)
- 841 [40] Thirumoorthy, K., Gokulakrishnan, B., Satishkumar, G., Landau, M.V., Wong Chi
842 Man, M., Oliviero, E., Al-doped magnetite encapsulated in mesoporous carbon: a long-
843 lasting Fenton catalyst for CWPO of phenol in a fixed-bed reactor under mild conditions,
844 *Catal. Sci. & Technol.* 11 (2021), 7368-7379. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1CY01218E>
- 845
846

- 847 [41] Li, B., Wei, Y.G., Wang, H., Yang, Y.D., Reduction of magnetite from copper
848 smelting slag using petro-diesel and biodiesel. *ISIJ Int.* 58 (2018), 1168-1174.
849 <https://doi.org/10.2355/isijinternational.ISIJINT-2017-723>
- 850 [42] Labus, M., Pyrite thermal decomposition in source rocks, *Fuel* 287 (2021) 119529.
851 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.119529>
- 852 [43] Liu, L.H., Liu, Q.F., Zang, S., Li, Y.K., Yang, L.T., The thermal transformation
853 behavior and products of pyrite during the coal gangue combustion, *Fuel* 324 (2022),
854 124803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.124803>
- 855 [44] Aracena, A., Jerez, O., Mechanism and kinetics of pyrite transformation at elevated
856 temperatures. *Physicochem. Probl. Miner. Process.* 57 (2021) 127-139.
857 <https://doi.org/10.37190/ppmp/143124>
- 858 [45] Ruan, S.F., Wang, C.Y., Jie, X.W., Yin, F., Zang, Y.L., Yao, Z.C., Chen, Y.Q.,
859 Kinetics of pyrite multi-step thermal decomposition in refractory gold sulphide
860 concentrates. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 147 (2022), 3689-3702.
861 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-021-10761-y>
- 862 [46] Wang, M., Du, Q., Li, Y.P., Xu, J.J., Gao, J.M., Wang, H., Effect of steam on the
863 transformation of sulfur during demineralized coal pyrolysis, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 140
864 (2019) 161-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2019.03.011>
- 865 [47] Warzinski, R.P., Friedman, S., LaCount, R.B., Air/water oxidative desulfurization
866 of coal and sulfur-containing compounds. *AIP Conference Proceedings* 70 (1981), 457-
867 458.
- 868 [48] Liu, S.Q., Ma, W.P., Zang, Y.X., Zang, Y.J., Qi, K.L., Sequential transformation
869 behavior of iron-bearing minerals during underground coal gasification, *Minerals* 8
870 (2018) 90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min8030090>
- 871 [49] Toyama, S., Kawamura, M., On the relationship between the bloating of lightweight
872 aggregate and reaction progress of the constituents, *J. Chem. Eng. Jpn.* 4 (1971) 251-
873 256. <https://doi.org/10.1252/jcej.4.251>
- 874 [50] Huang, J.C., Tao, L., Tie, W.B., Li, Z.X., Wang, Q., Liu, Z.S., Transport properties
875 of CO₂ in different reactivity coke solution loss reaction based on Stefan flow theory,
876 *ACS Omega* 5 (2020) 26817-26828. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c03913>
- 877 [51] Firdiyono, F., Handayani, M., Sulistiyono, E., Antoro, I.D., Preliminary comparative
878 study on the adsorption of minor elements in sodium silicate solution. *Maj. Metalurgi* 27
879 (2016) 15-26. <https://doi.org/10.14203/metalurgi.v27i1.135>
- 880 [52] Prasetio, A.B., Maksum, A., Soedarsono, J.W., Firdiyono, F., Thermal
881 characteristics of ferronickel slag on roasting process with addition of sodium carbonate
882 (Na₂CO₃), *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 541 (2019) 012037.
883 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/541/1/012037>
- 884 [53] Wang, H., Feng, Q.M., Liu, K., Li, Z.S., Tang, X.K., Li, G.Z., Highly efficient
885 fluoride adsorption from aqueous solution by nepheline prepared from kaolinite through
886 alkali-hydrothermal process. *J. Environ. Manag.* 196 (2017) 72-79.
887 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.015>
- 888 [54] Chen, N.C., Wu, W.H, Li, Z., Deng, A.P., XRD and morphologic analysis of alpha-
889 cristobalite produced from silica mine waste under lower calcination temperature, *Adv.*
890 *Struct. Mater.* 686 (2011) 692-695.
891 <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.686.692>
- 892 [55] Nanri, H., Takeuchi, N., Ishida, S., Watanabe, K., Wakamatsu, M., Mineralizing
893 action of iron in amorphous silica, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 203 (1996) 375-379,
894 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3093\(96\)00371-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3093(96)00371-7)

895 [56] Solihin S., Rizqiadi, A., Handayani, I., An analysis of the formation mechanism of
 896 geopolymer made from obsidian mineral and its potential application as slow release
 897 fertilizer. *Anal. Sci.* 36 (2020), 1401-1406. <https://doi.org/10.2116/analsci.20P182>
 898 [57] Koch-Müller, M., Cemic, L., Langer, K., Experimental and thermodynamic study of
 899 Fe-Mg exchange between olivine and ortho-pyroxene in the system MgO-FeO-SiO₂, *Eur.*
 900 *J. Mineral.* 4 (1992) 115-135. doi: [10.1127/ejm/4/1/0115](https://doi.org/10.1127/ejm/4/1/0115)
 901 [58] Koch-Müller, M., Rhede, D., Schulz, R., Wirth, R., Breakdown of hydrous
 902 ringwoodite to pyroxene and spinelloid at high P and T and oxidizing conditions. *Phys.*
 903 *Chem. Miner.* 36 (2009) 329–341. doi:[10.1007/s00269-008-0281-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-008-0281-z)
 904 [59] Liu, Y.H., Guan, Y., Zang, Y.D., Xiong, Y., Effect of atmosphere on mineral
 905 transformation of Zhundong coal during gasification in CO₂/H₂O, *Fuel* 310 (2022)
 906 122428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2021.122428>

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908 **Figures**

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911 **Figure 1.** Percentage of amorphous phase found in the aggregates once they have been fired (*Am. Ph.₂*) as
 912 a function of the metallic iron percentage in the raw materials (*Fe₁*). *R*²: coefficient of determination

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915 **Tables**

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917 **Table 1.** Mineralogical composition (wt %) of the raw materials used to manufacture the
 918 artificial aggregates studied

Raw material	Kaolinite-rich component (<i>Krc</i>)	Iron phase (<i>IP</i>)				Cork powder (<i>Ck</i>)	Sodium carbonate (<i>Na₂CO₃</i>)
		Fe	Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe ₃ O ₄	FeS ₂		
Mineralogical composition	Kaolinite: 84.9 % Quartz: 12.6 % Illite: 2.5%	Metallic iron: 100 %	Hematite: 100 %	Magnetite: 100 %	Pyrite: 78.6% Rhomboclase: 16.1% Cookeite: 3.2% Illite: 2.1%	No mineralogical phase; 100% amorphous phase	Natrite: 100%

926 **Table 2.** Percentage (wt%) of amorphous material and crystalline phases detected in aggregates
927 manufactured without any iron phase (*N.I.P-type*), with metallic iron (*Fe-type*), hematite (*Fe₂O₃-type*),
928 magnetite (*Fe₃O₄-type*) or pyrite (*FeS₂-type*). **Am. Ph.:** amorphous phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Fe:**
929 metallic iron; **Crs:** cristobalite; **Hem:** hematite; **Mag:** magnetite; **Hc:** hercynite; **Clp:** clinopyroxenes; **Fa:**
930 fayalite; **Tr:** troilite; **Nep:** nepheline; **GoF:** goodness of fit; **Rwp:** weighted R profile; **Ex:** aggregate layer;
931 **In:** aggregate core; **Op:** optimum aggregate for a certain property. Blank space: not detected

Type	Aggregate Code	Am. Ph.	Mul	Qtz	Fe	Crs	Hem	Mag	Hc	Clp	Fa	Tr	Nep	GoF	Rwp	
<i>N.I.P</i>	<i>1-N.I.P</i>	52.2	42.9	4.8	0.1									4.5	6.8	
	<i>4-N.I.P</i>	59.4	36.7	3.7	0.2									3.7	4.8	
	<i>5-N.I.P</i>	61.6	34.3	4.0	0.1									3.9	5.9	
	<i>10-N.I.P</i>	56.9	38.4	4.7	0.1									3.8	5.7	
<i>Fe</i>	<i>11-Fe</i>	61.2	34.5	2.2	0.4	1.7								2.8	3.1	
	<i>15-Fe</i>	63.4	26.5	1.2	0.7	8.2								2.7	2.4	
	<i>17-Fe</i>	69.3	24.3	2.3	1.0		1.2		1.9					2.6	2.5	
	<i>18-Fe</i>	69.1	25.9	1.4	1.1		1.5		1.1					2.6	2.5	
	<i>27-Fe</i>	69.9	11.2	2.1	1.7	6.5	1.1		7.5					2.8	2.3	
	<i>30-Fe (Ex)</i>	66.9			0.2		4.5	8.9	15.4		4.1			3.1	2.2	
	<i>30-Fe (In)</i>	84.0	8.1	0.7	1.4				5.8					4.1	3.8	
	<i>32-Fe</i>	59.0	14.3	2.6	1.8	7.4	7.5		7.3					2.6	2.1	
	<i>33-Fe</i>	80.9	7.3	1.7	2.3		1.3	1.8	4.8					2.1	1.8	
	<i>34-Fe</i>	80.3	5.9	1.2	2.3		1.5	3.7	5.1					2.3	1.9	
	<i>36-Fe</i>	81.3	3.0	2.5	2.0		2.3	4.8	4.1					2.2	2.7	
	<i>Op-Fe (BI)</i>	57.5	17.7	2.9	0.9	7.6	7.5		5.9					1.9	2.3	
	<i>Op-Fe (prd)</i>	54.9	28.6	2.9	0.4	13.2								2.2	2.8	
	<i>Op-Fe (WA₂₄)</i>	56.9	38.4	4.7	0.1									3.8	5.7	
<i>Op-Fe (S)</i>	62.1	34.9	2.0	0.2		0.8							2.3	3.4		
<i>Fe₂O₃</i>	<i>19-Fe₂O₃</i>	40.1	34.0	3.1		7.0	11.5			4.3				2.6	2.1	
	<i>19-Fe₂O₃ (In)</i>	45.3	31.9	0.8		5.1	9.4			7.4				3.3	1.9	
	<i>25-Fe₂O₃</i>	61.6	13.7	0.6		2.7	17.3			4.1				2.6	1.8	
	<i>27-Fe₂O₃</i>	53.0	14.7	0.4		8.8	23.1							2.3	1.7	
	<i>29-Fe₂O₃</i>	60.1	11.8	1.3			26.8							2.5	1.7	
	<i>32-Fe₂O₃</i>	57.1	8.0	0.6		8.3	22.1			3.9				2.9	1.9	
	<i>32-Fe₂O₃ (In)</i>	59.9	5.8			6.9	21.2			6.1				2.6	1.9	
	<i>33-Fe₂O₃</i>	72.7	3.3				23.9							2.3	1.6	
	<i>36-Fe₂O₃</i>	76.0					12.3	11.7						1.9	1.3	
	<i>36-Fe₂O₃ (In)</i>	68.7					8.3	23.0						1.9	1.3	
	<i>Op-Fe₂O₃ (BI, prd)</i>	52.9	17.8	0.5		8.0	18.4			2.4				1.9	1.9	
	<i>Op-Fe₂O₃ (WA₂₄)</i>	65.6	22.1	1.4		0.5	5.8		1.5	3.2				2.0	2.3	
	<i>Op-Fe₂O₃ (S)</i>	59.9	10.1	1.0			27.9			1.0				1.8	1.2	
	<i>Fe₃O₄</i>	<i>12-Fe₃O₄</i>	47.0	41.8	1.9		7.6		1.6						3.5	3.2
<i>16-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		33.6	37.9	1.0		15.6	9.8	2.1						2.8	2.3	
<i>16-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		43.8	35.3			8.8	5.7	6.5						3.0	2.5	
<i>19-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		47.0	27.2	2.4		10.2	5.9	0.8	3.6	2.9				3.1	2.5	
<i>19-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		69.6	21.3	0.5		2.1	1.3		5.2					2.0	1.6	
<i>20-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		58.2	14.0	2.0		1.6	5.5	4.5	11.4	2.8				3.3	2.6	
<i>20-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		68.0		2.0		6.3		6.8	16.9					2.8	2.2	
<i>25-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		67.1	9.6			1.6	7.0	8.2		6.5				3.0	2.2	
<i>25-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		71.5							28.5					2.1	1.5	
<i>28-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		66.2		1.0		4.8	9.9	15.1		3.0				2.3	1.5	
<i>28-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		74.8				0.9	1.4	12.8	10.1					2.1	1.4	
<i>32-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		70.4		2.7		0.8	7.3	18.9						2.0	1.3	
<i>32-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		80.2		0.5			1.2	18.1						2.0	1.3	
<i>35-Fe₃O₄ (Ex)</i>		73.2					4.7	18.3			3.8			1.8	1.2	
<i>35-Fe₃O₄ (In)</i>		60.3					1.4	6.7	14.9		16.7			1.8	1.2	
<i>Op-Fe₃O₄ (BI, prd)</i>		70.3		3.5		3.9	7.0	15.3						1.8	1.8	
<i>Op-Fe₃O₄ (WA₂₄)</i>		70.4		3.9			5.2	1.6	5.0	13.8				2.2	2.4	
<i>Op-Fe₃O₄ (S)</i>		50.8	44.8	3.5		0.9		0.1						2.8	4.7	
<i>FeS₂</i>	<i>11-FeS₂</i>	52.0	43.6	3.0		1.5								3.4	4.7	
	<i>19-FeS₂</i>	57.7	36.8	4.5			0.5					0.9		3.2	4.3	
	<i>20-FeS₂</i>	56.0	41.6	2.4										3.1	3.9	
	<i>23-FeS₂</i>	54.1	41.1	2.4		1.3							1.1	2.8	3.1	
	<i>26-FeS₂</i>	58.2	37.4	3.7			0.8							3.1	3.2	
	<i>30-FeS₂</i>	35.4	48.3	1.3		13.5	0.9		0.7					3.4	3.4	
	<i>33-FeS₂ (Ex)</i>	53.7	2.7	0.5			5.9							37.2	3.6	3.5
	<i>33-FeS₂ (In)</i>	54.1	36.1	4.1									5.7	2.6	2.6	
	<i>36-FeS₂</i>	63.2	30.8	2.9			0.9						2.1	2.6	2.6	
	<i>Op-FeS₂ (BI)</i>	50.3	38.9	5.0			1.3							4.4	2.9	4.8
	<i>Op-FeS₂ (prd)</i>	61.3	30.9	6.8										1.0	3.3	6.4
	<i>Op-FeS₂ (WA₂₄)</i>	56.9	38.4	4.7	0.1										3.8	5.7
<i>Op-FeS₂ (S)</i>	54.2	38.6	2.6									4.6		2.3	3.5	

932 **Table 3.** Artificial aggregates produced without any iron phase (*N.I.P-type*). Comparison between the
 933 percentage of crystalline phases and amorphous material in the raw materials (RM) and in the artificial
 934 aggregates manufactured with 100 g of that raw material (AA). **LOI (I+2):** loss on ignition during the
 935 preheating and heating phases; **Kln:** kaolinite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Ill:** illite; **Nat:** natrite; **Am. Ph.:** amorphous
 936 phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Fe:** metallic iron; **(Ck):** coming from the cork powder. Blank space: not detected
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Aggregate Code		LOI (I+2)	Kln	Qtz	Ill	Nat	Am. Ph.	Mul	Fe
1-N.I.P	RM		84.9	12.6	2.5				
	AA	13.0		4.2			45.4	37.3	0.1
4-N.I.P	RM		80.7	12.0	2.4		5 (Ck)		
	AA	16.9		3.1			49.3	30.5	0.2
5-N.I.P	RM		80.7	12.0	2.4	5			
	AA	15.2		3.4			52.3	29.1	0.1
10-N.I.P	RM		76.4	11.3	2.3	5	5 (Ck)		
	AA	19.4		3.8			45.8	30.9	0.1

938 **Table 4.** Artificial aggregates produced with metallic iron phase (*Fe-type*). Comparison between the
 939 percentage of crystalline phases and amorphous material in the raw materials (RM) and in the artificial
 940 aggregates manufactured with 100 g of that raw material (AA). **LOI (I+2):** loss on ignition during the
 941 preheating and heating phases; **Kln:** kaolinite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Ill:** illite; **Fe:** metallic iron; **Nat:** natrite; **Am.**
 942 **Ph.:** amorphous phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Crs:** cristobalite; **Hem:** hematite; **Mag:** magnetite; **Hc:** hercynite;
 943 **Fa:** fayalite; **(Ck):** coming from the cork powder; **Ex:** aggregate layer; **In:** aggregate core; **Op:** optimum
 944 aggregate for a certain property. Blank space: not detected
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Aggregate Code		LOI (I+2)	Kln	Qtz	Ill	Fe	Nat	Am. Ph.	Mul	Crs	Hem	Mag	Hc	Fa
11-Fe	RM		72.2	10.7	2.1	12.5	1.25	1.25(Ck)						
	AA	11.2		2.0		0.4		54.3	30.6	1.5				
15-Fe	RM		63.7	9.5	1.9	25								
	AA	5.9		1.1		0.7		59.7	24.9	7.7				
17-Fe	RM		61.6	9.1	1.8	25	2.5							
	AA	7.6		2.1		0.9		64.0	22.4		1.1		1.8	
18-Fe	RM		59.4	8.8	1.8	25	5							
	AA	9.7		1.3		1.0		62.4	23.4		1.4		1.0	
27-Fe	RM		42.5	6.3	1.3	50								
	AA	2.6		2.0		1.7		68.1	10.9	6.3	1.1		7.3	
30-Fe	RM		38.2	5.7	1.1	50	2.5	2.5 (Ck)						
	AA(Ex)	4.5				0.2		63.9			4.3	8.5	14.7	3.9
	AA(In)	4.5		0.7		1.3		80.3	7.7				5.5	
32-Fe	RM		38.2	5.7	1.1	50		5 (Ck)						
	AA	6.6		2.4		1.7		55.1	13.4	6.9	7.0		6.8	
33-Fe	RM		38.2	5.7	1.1	50	5							
	AA	4.6		1.6		2.2		77.1	7.0		1.2	1.7	4.6	
34-Fe	RM		36.1	5.4	1.1	50	5	2.5 (Ck)						
	AA	5.3		1.1		2.2		76.0	5.6		1.4	3.5	4.8	
36-Fe	RM		34.0	5.0	1.0	50	5	5 (Ck)						
	AA	8.4		2.3		1.8		74.5	2.7		2.1	4.4	3.8	
Op-Fe (Bl)	RM		48.2	7.2	1.4	39.7		3.5 (Ck)						
	AA	6.3		2.7		0.8		53.9	16.6	7.1	7.0		5.5	
Op-Fe (prd)	RM		58.4	8.7	1.7	26.2		5 (Ck)						
	AA	11.0		2.6		0.4		48.9	25.5	11.7				
Op-Fe(WA₂₄)	RM		76.4	11.3	2.3		5	5 (Ck)						
	AA	19.4		3.8		0.1		45.8	30.9					
Op-Fe(S)	RM		74.8	11.1	2.2	10.0	1.9							
	AA	9.6		1.8		0.2		56.1	31.5		0.7			

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Table 5. Artificial aggregates produced with hematite (Fe_2O_3 -type). Comparison between the percentage of crystalline phases and amorphous material in the raw materials (RM) and in the artificial aggregates manufactured with 100 g of that raw material (AA). **LOI (I+2):** loss on ignition during the preheating and heating phases; **Kln:** kaolinite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Ill:** illite; **Hem:** hematite; **Nat:** natrite; **Am. Ph.:** amorphous phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Crs:** cristobalite; **Mag:** magnetite; **Hc:** hercynite; **Clp:** clinopyroxenes; (**Ck**): coming from the cork powder; **In:** aggregate core; **Op:** optimum aggregate for a certain property. Blank space: not detected

Aggregate Code		LOI (I+2)	Kln	Qtz	Ill	Hem	Nat	Am. Ph.	Mul	Crs	Mag	Hc	Clp
19- Fe_2O_3	RM		59.4	8.8	1.8	25		5 (Ck)					
	AA	14.4		2.7		9.8		34.3	29.1	6.0			3.7
	AA(In)	14.4		0.7		8.0		38.8	27.3	4.4			6.3
25- Fe_2O_3	RM		48.8	7.2	1.4	37.5	1.25	3.75(Ck)					
	AA	12.1		0.5		15.2		54.1	12.0	2.4			3.6
27- Fe_2O_3	RM		42.5	6.3	1.3	50							
	AA	6.6		0.4		21.6		49.5	13.7	8.2			
29- Fe_2O_3	RM		40.3	6.0	1.2	50	2.5						
	AA	7.2		1.2		24.9		55.8	11.0				
32- Fe_2O_3	RM		38.2	5.7	1.1	50		5 (Ck)					
	AA	14.3		0.5		19.0		49.0	6.9	7.1			3.3
	AA(In)	14.3				18.2		51.4	5.0	5.9			5.2
33- Fe_2O_3	RM		38.2	5.7	1.1	50	5						
	AA	7.9				22.0		67.0	3.0				
36- Fe_2O_3	RM		34.0	5.0	1.0	50	5	5 (Ck)					
	AA	14.1				10.6		65.3			10.1		
	AA(In)	14.1				7.1		59.0			19.8		
Op- Fe_2O_3 (BI, prd)	RM		48.2	7.2	1.4	38.2		5 (Ck)					
	AA	12.6		0.4		16.1		46.2	15.6	7.0			2.1
Op- Fe_2O_3 (WA ₂₄)	RM		61.1	9.1	1.8	18.3	5	4.7 (Ck)					
	AA	16.3		1.2		4.9		54.9	18.5	0.4		1.3	2.7
Op- Fe_2O_3 (S)	RM		40.1	5.9	1.2	50	2.8						
	AA	7.5		0.9		25.8		55.4	9.3				0.9

996 **Table 6.** Artificial aggregates produced with magnetite (Fe_3O_4 -type). Comparison between the percentage
 997 of crystalline phases and amorphous material in the raw materials (RM) and in the artificial aggregates
 998 manufactured with 100 g of that raw material (AA). **LOI (I+2):** loss on ignition during the preheating and
 999 heating phases; **Kln:** kaolinite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Ill:** illite; **Mag:** magnetite; **Nat:** natrite; **Am. Ph.:** amorphous
 1000 phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Crs:** cristobalite; **Hem:** hematite; **Hc:** hercynite; **Fa:** Fayalite; **Clp:** clinopyroxenes;
 1001 (**Ck:**) coming from the cork powder; **Ex:** aggregate layer; **In:** aggregate core; **Op:** optimum aggregate for
 1002 a certain property. Blank space: not detected
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Aggregate Code	LOI (I+2)	Kln	Qtz	Ill	Mag	Nat	Am. Ph.	Mul	Crs	Hem	Hc	Others
12- Fe_3O_4	RM	70.0	10.4	2.1	12.5	1.25	3.75(Ck)					
	AA	15.0	1.6		1.4		40.0	35.6	6.5			
16- Fe_3O_4	RM	61.6	9.1	1.8	25		2.5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	12.3	0.9		1.8		29.5	33.2	13.7	8.6		
	AA(In)	12.3			5.7		38.4	31.0	7.7	5.0		
19- Fe_3O_4	RM	59.4	8.8	1.8	25		5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	16.7	2.0		0.7		39.2	22.7	8.5	4.9	3.0	Clp: 2.4
	AA(In)	16.7	0.4				58.0	17.7	1.7	1.1	4.3	
20- Fe_3O_4	RM	57.3	8.5	1.7	25	2.5	5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	15.7	1.7		3.8		49.1	11.8	1.3	4.6	9.6	Clp: 2.4
	AA(In)	15.7	1.7		5.7		57.3		5.3		14.2	
25- Fe_3O_4	RM	48.8	7.2	1.4	37.5	1.25	3.75(Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	14.5			7.0		57.4	8.2	1.4	6.0		Clp: 5.6
	AA(In)	14.5					61.2				24.4	
28- Fe_3O_4	RM	40.3	6.0	1.2	50		2.5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	10.5	0.9		13.5		59.2		4.3	8.9		Clp: 2.7
	AA(In)	10.5			11.5		67.0		0.8	1.3	9.0	
32- Fe_3O_4	RM	38.2	5.7	1.1	50		5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	13.5	2.3		16.3		60.9		0.7	6.3		
	AA(In)	13.5	0.4		15.7		69.3			1.0		
35- Fe_3O_4	RM	36.1	5.4	1.1	50	2.5	5 (Ck)					
	AA(Ex)	14.7			15.6		62.4			4.0		Fa: 3.2
	AA(In)	14.7			5.7		51.4			1.2	12.7	Fa: 14.2
Op- Fe_3O_4 (BI, prd)	RM	47.5	7.1	1.4	40.1		3.9 (Ck)					
	AA	12.5	3.1		13.4		61.5		3.4	6.1		
Op- Fe_3O_4 (WA ₂₄)	RM	56.1	8.3	1.7	23.9	5	5 (Ck)					
	AA	15.8	3.3		1.3		59.3			4.4	4.2	Clp: 11.6
Op- Fe_3O_4 (S)	RM	77.9	11.6	2.3	5.6	2.6						
	AA	12.5	3.1		0.1		44.4	39.2	0.8			

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Table 7. Artificial aggregates produced with pyrite (FeS_2 -type). Comparison between the percentage of crystalline phases and amorphous material in the raw materials (RM) and in the artificial aggregates manufactured with 100 g of that raw material (AA). **LOI (I+2):** loss on ignition during the preheating and heating phases; **Kln:** kaolinite; **Qtz:** quartz; **Ill:** illite; **Py:** pyrite; **Rhmb.:** rhomboclase; **Ckt.:** cookeite; **Nat:** natrite; **Am. Ph.:** amorphous phase; **Mul:** mullite; **Crs:** cristobalite; **Hem:** hematite; **Tr:** troilite; **Hc:** hercynite; **Nep:** nepheline; **Fe:** metallic iron; **(Ck):** coming from the cork powder; **Ex:** aggregate layer; **In:** aggregate core; **Op:** optimum aggregate for a certain property. Blank space: not detected

Aggregate Code	LOI (I+2)	Kln	Qtz	Ill	Py	Rhmb	Ckt	Nat	Am. Ph.	Mul	Crs	Hem	Others
11- FeS_2	RM		79.6	11.8	2.5	2.9	0.6	0.1	1.25	1.25(Ck)			
	AA	15.3		2.5					44.1	36.9	1.3		
19- FeS_2	RM		74.3	11.0	2.4	5.9	1.2	0.2	5				
	AA	15.9		3.7					48.5	30.9		0.2	Tro: 0.8
20- FeS_2	RM		72.2	10.7	2.3	5.9	1.2	0.2	2.5	5 (Ck)			
	AA	19.6		1.9					45.0	33.4			
23- FeS_2	RM		73.2	10.9	2.4	8.8	1.8	0.4	1.25	1.25 (Ck)			
	AA	16.5		2.0					45.2	34.3	1.1		Tro: 0.9
26- FeS_2	RM		69.0	10.2	2.2	8.8	1.8	0.4	3.75	3.75 (Ck)			
	AA	19.6		3.0					46.8	30.1		0.6	
30- FeS_2	RM		67.9	10.1	2.3	11.8	2.4	0.5		5 (Ck)			
	AA	21.2		1.0					28.0	38.1	10.6	0.7	Hc: 0.6
33- FeS_2	RM		67.9	10.1	2.3	11.8	2.4	0.5	5				
	AA(Ex)	17.3		0.4					44.4	2.2		4.9	Nep: 30.8
	AA(In)	17.3		3.4					44.7	29.9			Tro: 4.7
36- FeS_2	RM		63.7	9.5	2.2	11.8	2.4	0.5	5	5 (Ck)			
	AA	21.5		2.3					49.6	24.2		0.7	Tro: 1.6
Op- FeS_2 (BI)	RM		74.4	11.0	2.3	5.3	1.1	0.2	5	0.7 (Ck)			
	AA	16.1		4.2					42.2	32.6		1.1	Nep: 3.7
Op- FeS_2 (prd)	RM		74.9	11.1	2.2	1.4	0.3	0.1	5	5 (Ck)			
	AA	18.8		5.5					49.8	25.1			Nep: 0.8
Op- FeS_2 (WA ₂₄)	RM		76.4	11.3	2.3				5	5 (Ck)			
	AA	19.4		3.8					45.8	30.9			Fe: 0.1
Op- FeS_2 (S)	RM		70.5	10.5	2.4	11.8	2.4	0.5	2				
	AA	15.9		2.2					45.6	32.5			Tro: 3.9

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Table 8 (Continues). Possible reactions from which minerals have been newly formed and type of atmosphere that could favour its formation. [Corresponding reaction in the manuscript]

Newly formed mineral	From	Possible reaction/s	Atmosphere	Based on:
Mullite (3Al₂O₃•2SiO₂)	Kaolinite (Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O)	Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O + (T ⁿ >1000°C) → (γ-alumina or aluminium-silicon spinel and/or mullite) + (amorphous silica and/or α-cristobalite) + <i>LOI</i> [Rc. 1]		[20,21,22]
Cristobalite (SiO₂)	Kaolinite (Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O)	Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O + (T ⁿ >1000°C) → (γ-alumina or aluminium-silicon spinel and/or mullite) + (amorphous silica and/or α-cristobalite) + <i>LOI</i> [Rc. 1]		[20,21,22]
Hematite (Fe₂O₃)	Metallic iron (Fe ⁰)	2Fe ⁰ + 3/2 O ₂ → Fe₂O₃	Oxidizing	[12,28]
	Magnetite (Fe ₃ O ₄)	2Fe ₃ O ₄ + 1/2 O ₂ → 3Fe₂O₃ [Rc. 9]	Oxidizing	[38]
	Pyrite (FeS ₂)	FeS ₂ + 11/4 O ₂ → 1/2 Fe₂O₃ + 2SO ₂ [Rc. 6]	Oxidizing	[44]
Magnetite (Fe₃O₄)	Metallic iron (Fe ⁰)	3Fe ⁰ + H ₂ O → Fe₃O₄ + 8H ⁺ + 8e ⁻	Oxidizing	
	Hematite (Fe ₂ O ₃)	3Fe ₂ O ₃ + CO → 2Fe₃O₄ + CO ₂	Reducing	
		3Fe ₂ O ₃ + H ₂ → 2Fe₃O₄ + H ₂ O [Rc. 7]	Reducing	
Hercynite (FeAl₂O₄)	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and metallic iron (Fe ⁰)	a). 2Fe ⁰ + O ₂ → 2FeO [Rc. 2] b). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 3] c). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl₂O₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]	a) Oxidizing	[32,33]
	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and hematite (Fe ₂ O ₃)	a). Fe ₂ O ₃ → 2FeO + 1/2 O ₂ [Rc. 8] b). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 3] c). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl₂O₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]	a) Reducing	
	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and magnetite (Fe ₃ O ₄)	a). Fe ₃ O ₄ → 3FeO + 1/2 O ₂ [Rc. 22] b). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 3] c). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl₂O₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]	a) Reducing	
	Kaolinite (Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O) and magnetite (Fe ₃ O ₄)	Al ₂ O ₃ + 0.25 Fe ₃ O ₄ + 0.25 Fe ⁰ → FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 10]	Reducing	[40]
	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and pyrite (FeS ₂)	a). FeS ₂ + O ₂ → Fe ₇ S ₈ + 6SO ₂ [Rc. 11] b). 2Fe ₇ S ₈ + 53/2O ₂ → 7Fe ₂ O ₃ + 16SO ₂ [Rc. 12] c). Fe ₂ O ₃ → 2FeO + 1/2 O ₂ [Rc. 8] d). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 3] e). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl₂O₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]	a) Oxidizing b) Oxidizing c) Reducing	[32,33]
		a). FeS ₂ + O ₂ → Fe ₇ S ₈ + 6SO ₂ [Rc. 11] b). 3Fe ₇ S ₈ + 38O ₂ → 7Fe ₃ O ₄ + 24SO ₂ c). Fe ₃ O ₄ → 3FeO + 1/2 O ₂ [Rc. 22] d). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl₂O₄ [Rc. 3] e). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl₂O₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]	a) Oxidizing b) Oxidizing c) Reducing	

Table 8 (Continued). Possible reactions from which minerals have been newly formed and type of atmosphere that could favour its formation. [Corresponding reaction in the manuscript]

Newly formed mineral	From	Possible reaction/s	Atmosphere	Based on
Fayalite (Fe ₂ SiO ₄)	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and metallic iron (Fe ⁰)	a). 2Fe ⁰ + O ₂ → 2FeO [Rc. 2]	a) Oxidizing	[32,33]
		b). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl ₂ O ₄ [Rc. 3]		
		a). 2Fe ⁰ + O ₂ → 2FeO [Rc. 2]	a) Oxidizing	
	b). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl ₂ O ₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]			
	c). Fe ₂ O ₃ + SiO ₂ → Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + ½ O ₂ [Rc. 5]			
	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and magnetite (Fe ₃ O ₄)	a). Fe ₃ O ₄ → 3FeO + ½ O ₂ [Rc. 22]	a) Reducing	
		b). 3FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 3FeAl ₂ O ₄ + 2SiO ₂ [Rc. 4]		
		c). Fe ₂ O ₃ + SiO ₂ → Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + ½ O ₂ [Rc. 5]		
Clinopyroxenes (ferrosilite, FeSiO ₃)	Mullite (Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃) and magnetite (Fe ₃ O ₄)	a). Fe ₃ O ₄ → 3FeO + ½ O ₂ [Rc. 22]	a) Reducing	[58]
		b). 7FeO + Al ₆ Si ₂ O ₁₃ → 2Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + 3FeAl ₂ O ₄ [Rc. 3]		
		c). Fe ₂ SiO ₄ + O ₂ → 6FeSiO ₃ + 5Fe _{2.40} Si _{0.60} O ₄ [Rc. 23]	c) Oxidizing	
Troilite (FeS)	Pyrite (FeS ₂)	a). 2(1-x)FeS ₂ → 2Fe _(1-x) S + (1-2x)S ₂ [Rc. 13]	Reducing	[46,47]
		b). Fe _(1-x) S → (1-x)FeS + (x/2)S ₂ [Rc. 14]		
Nepheline ((Na,K)AlSiO ₄)	Kaolinite (Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O) and natrite (Na ₂ CO ₃)	a) Na ₂ CO ₃ → Na ₂ O + CO ₂ [Rc. 20]		[51]
		b) Na ₂ O + SiO ₂ (silicates) → Na ₂ SiO ₃ [Rc. 21]		
Amorphous phase	Kaolinite (Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O)	Al ₂ O ₃ •2SiO ₂ •2H ₂ O + (T ⁿ >1000°C) → (γ-alumina or aluminium-silicon spinel and/or mullite) + (amorphous silica and/or α-cristobalite) + LOI [Rc. 1]		[20,21,22]

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Table 9. Review of the evolution suffered by each mineralogical phase (rows) found in the raw materials (*RM*) and/or in the artificial aggregates (*AA*) depending on the iron phase added as raw material (columns). *Kln*: kaolinite; *Qtz*: quartz; *Ill*: illite; *Ck*: cork powder; *Nat*: natrite; *Fe*: metallic iron; *Hem*: hematite; *Mag*: magnetite; *Py*: pyrite; *Mul*: mullite; *Crs*: cristobalite; *Hc*: hercynite; *Fa*: fayalite; *Clp*: clinopyroxenes; *Tro*: troilite; *Nep*: nepheline; *Am. Ph.*: amorphous phase; *LOI*: loss on ignition

Mineral	Iron phase in the raw materials (Type of artificial aggregate)				
	No iron phase (<i>N.I.P</i>)	Metallic iron (<i>Fe</i>)	Hematite (<i>Fe₂O₃</i>)	Magnetite (<i>Fe₃O₄</i>)	Pyrite (<i>FeS₂</i>)
<i>Kln</i>	<i>RM</i> To: Mul, Fe, Am. Ph., LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Crs, Hc, Fa, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Crs, Hc, Clp, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Crs, Hc, Fa, Clp, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul, Crs, Hc, Nep, Amp. Ph., LOI
<i>Qtz</i>	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am. Ph.	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am. Ph.	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am. Ph.	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am. Ph.	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am. Ph.
<i>Ill</i>	<i>RM</i> To: Mul, Fe, Am. Ph., LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Hc, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Clp, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Clp, Am. Ph., LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: Mul*, Nep, Amp. Ph., LOI
<i>Ck</i>	<i>RM</i> To: LOI	<i>RM</i> To: LOI	<i>RM</i> To: LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: LOI*	<i>RM</i> To: LOI*
<i>Nat</i>	<i>RM</i> To: Am. Ph., LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Am. Ph., LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Clp, Am. Ph.*, LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Clp, Am. Ph., LOI	<i>RM</i> To: Nep, Am.Ph., LOI
<i>Fe</i>	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Hem*, Mag*, Hc*, Am. Ph.*, Fa, Mul			
<i>Hem</i>		<i>AA</i> From: Fe*	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Am.Ph.*, Mag, Hc, Clp, Mul	<i>AA</i> From: Mag*	<i>AA</i> From: Py
<i>Mag</i>		<i>AA</i> From: Fe*	<i>AA</i> From: Hem	<i>RM > AA</i> To: Hem*, Hc*, Am. Ph.*, Fa, Clp, Mul	
<i>Py</i>					<i>RM</i> To: Hem, Tro*, Am.Ph., Mul, Hc, LOI
<i>Mul</i>	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill	<i>AA</i> From: Kln*, Ill*, Fe	<i>AA</i> From: Kln*, Ill*, Hem	<i>AA</i> From: Kln*, Ill*, Mag	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill, Py
<i>Crs</i>		<i>AA</i> From: Kln	<i>AA</i> From: Kln	<i>AA</i> From: Kln	<i>AA</i> From: Kln
<i>Hc</i>		<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill, Fe*	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Hem	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Mag*	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Py
<i>Fa</i>		<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Fe		<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Mag	
<i>Clp</i>			<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill, Nat, Hem	<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill, Nat, Mag	
<i>Tro</i>					<i>AA</i> From: Py*
<i>Nep</i>					<i>AA</i> From: Kln, Ill, Nat
<i>Am. Ph.</i>	<i>RM < AA</i> From: Kln, Qtz, Ill, Nat	<i>RM < AA</i> From: Kln, Qtz, Ill, Nat, Fe*	<i>RM < AA</i> From: Kln, Qtz, Ill, Nat*, Hem*	<i>RM < AA</i> From: Kln, Qtz, Ill, Nat, Mag*	<i>RM < AA</i> From: Kln, Qtz, Ill, Nat, Py

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1 **Declaration of competing interest**

- 2 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
3 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper